

CONTENT SYNCRETISM IN TACTILE SENSORY QUALITIES

Teshaboeva Gulnoza

Andijan State University

Department of elementary education methodology
senior teacher

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Annotation: It is known that since the emergence of mankind, all kinds of things have lived with a passion for touching objects and understanding its properties. In language, however, one names what one perceives, what one undergoes a synthesis of perception, object, etc. Let them know their relationship. For this reason, it can be said that qualitative semantics, including the study of its syncretic nature, are also ancient. Of course, it is natural that linguists also studied tactile qualities in the process of studying the qualitative word category. Tactile sensation as an object of study of tactile qualities is considered important. In studies, it is argued that tactile qualities are also ancient in the process of studying tactile qualities.

Key words: linguistics, tactile adjectives, metaphor, semantics, understanding, syncretism, word order, lexical line, communication

In linguistics, the constant systematic regulation of language, the widespread use of its achievements, has been the focus of linguists. All changes in language, generational renewal and other types of changes have been important to increase language activity and create conditions for its communicative development. It was in lexical line units that the emergence of new meanings of existing words occurred in order to satisfy the naming needs of linguistic phenomena. These changes are related to the semantic level (similarity in names) on a metaphorical basis, or the migration of methanomics (by integrity) is considered a divigate of the development of the lexical system of the language¹.

It is known that since the emergence of mankind, all kinds of things have lived with a passion for touching objects and understanding its properties. In language, however, one names what one perceives, what one undergoes a synthesis of perception, object, etc. Let them know their relationship. For this reason, it can be said that qualitative semantics, including the study of its syncretic nature, are also ancient. Of course, it is natural that linguists also studied tactile qualities in the process of studying the qualitative word category. Tactile sensation as an object of study of tactile qualities is considered important. In studies, it is argued that tactile qualities are also ancient in the process of studying tactile qualities. At the same time, all things are associated with the fact that from time immemorial they have mvjudity and a special disposition. In the process of information transmission, all types of sensitivity are next to vision and hearing. The presence of a lexical-semantic group of adjectives associated with Touch is a productive source for the formation of synesthetic vocabulary. It is worth noting that in the formation of a linguistic image of the universe, semantic dictionaries of sensory perception (vocabulary of perception) form an important

¹ Кобякова И.А., Гарагин А.В., Филатова Н.И. Семантическая синкретизм осязательных прилагательных(на материале русского ,английского и иснанского языков)

layer of any language dictionary. Therefore, the study of sensory perception vocabulary is considered important by the property of expressiveness and expressiveness, which gives an expression of the concept about the features of the reflection of the universe. Many of the authors who study perceptual vocabulary operate with the acquisition of the position of cognitive linguists who study the opposite seven in the form of knowledge, concepts and categories about reality related to the process of knowledge of the universe."All human cognitive activity (cognition) can be considered the development of the universe's ability to act, and this activity is associated with the need to identify and distinguish between objects"².

It is known that perception is the reflection of objects and objects that affect the sensory organs in our consciousness as a whole, and not their certain properties, such as the sensory process. According to scientific teachings on sensations, things and their properties, components, properties, forms, action are considered primary, and the sensations themselves are the product of the influence of external and internal stimuli on the sensory organs. As the data show, the senses perceive the truthful image of material (objective) being, reality, consequently, when the material world has what it looks like, shape, character, they have the opportunity to reflect exactly, without any change, just like that³. The classification of tactile sensations is also foal, as is the description of qualities that represent taste, temperature and sense of smell. It can be said that thanks to touch, a person perceives everything in existence, the sign of objects and perceives it through this intuition. Of course, a person in the process of realizing this feature, it is assumed that knowledge of the sign of tactile qualities is associated with the participation of several organs. And to know, a person is able to first visually understand the shape and size of an object. Also, from motor skills (by touch), the comfort of clothing, the beauty of a person can be felt not only through visual touch. This touch is known in the process of making the fabric on the human EGN soft and elegant, pleasant.

It can be said that the sign of the mutual influence of different organs of perception on each other is manifested in units of language. A person perceives the world surrounding himself primarily through the sign of his tactile qualities of his own feeling. The five senses that were identified by Aristotle in ancient times and are still being debated in studies continue to be divided into: sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste, and to make different opinions about it. It is worth noting that there are many types of sensations, and in the process of cognitive activity of this person, the rut is formed, modified and replenished. It consists not only of visual, auditory, olfactory and taste sensations, including tactile, temperature and pain, vibration, muscle-joint and static-dynamic sensations. These types of intuition do not exist in isolation from each other, all sensory organs are always together in human activity, complementing each other Real reality in existence is considered important in bringing to the surface. However, it can also cause other analyzer-specific sensations when the sensory organs dictate each other, strengthening one by influencing its activity or, conversely, weakening it by halakitting it. In psychology, such a phenomenon is referred to as synesthesia. In many studies, the phenomenon of synesthesia, not only in human psychology,

² Маслова В.А. Введение в когнитивную лингвистику. М.: Флинта: Наука, 2011. С.15. (286 .с)

³ Ғозиев Э. Умумий психология. Психология мутахассислиги учун ўқув қўлланма II китоб Тошкент «Университет» 2000 .71-бет. (221-6)

balkim, N.D.Arutyunova, V.G.GAK, S.It has also been interpreted as a linguistic phenomenon in the work of linguists such as Ulmann⁴.

At the present stage of the development of linguistic science, the concept of synesthesia was developed by M.Ya.Sabanadze managed to give a definition, harmonizing it with a wide range, that is, psychological and linguistic approaches. "Synesthesia is a complex comprehensive linguopsychological phenomenon, and the sensations of one sensory modality will consist in inducing one second sensory in another modality. When linked to qualitative displacement at the psychological level, the linguistic level is linked to the displacement of meaning"⁵. Д.Юм идрокнинг ҳиссий табиати ҳақида баҳс юритар экан шундай хулоса келади. Унингча, олам инсонга сезги сифатида тақдим этилади". D.Such a conclusion comes when Yum argues about the emotional nature of perception. It is then that the universe is presented to man as intuition". Some sensations from different sensory organs can be temporarily contacted, but we will soon notice that they can be divided, recognized separately"⁶. In general, according to the Philosopher, all sensations arising from one object side correctly reflect the universe. One emotion alone, however, cannot give the image of what the object is originally. In other words, human cognitive activity does not proceed on the basis of only one isolated modality(monomodality). In contrast, perception as a complex form of emotional reflection is the result of the effects of multimodal and intramodal associative sensations. Perceptual modality refers to" information that regulates movement and activity, which is a way of making and processing"⁷. Questions and answers about the semantic nature of synesthesia are causing ambiguous interpretation by scientists. In this place are some authors, in particular, A.N.According to Veselovsky, the primary physiological Union of two different senses becomes a single intuition.⁸ Synesthesia is believed by some scholars to be different from the said positivity "in the intersection of the senses one can emphasize the intuitive desire of the mind to perceive the world without syncretic (singular) rather than discrete".⁹ This synesthesia is considered to be the third most common type of metaphorical manifestation that contrasts with positivity and is also welcomed by us. S.Ulman suggests that synaesthetic metaphors is the transfer of meanings associated with any sensory organ to areas that are related to another organ.¹⁰ Synesthesia practically affects whole word categories, especially independent word categories, the most important aspect is characteristic of the semantic features of the adjective word category. Since the

⁴ Арутюнова Н.Д.Язык и мир человека.М.:Языки русской культуры,1998..896.с. 5. Гак В.Г. Семантическая структура слова как компонент семантической структуры высказываний// Семантическая структура слова. М., 1971. 90 с. Ульманн С. Семантические универсалии// Новое в лингвистике. Вып. V (Языковые универсалии). М.: Прогресс, 1970. С. 250 – 299

⁵ *Сабанадзе М.Я.* Синестезия в подязыке музыковедения (на материале английского языка): автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. Ленинград, 1987С.12.(21 с.)

⁶ Юм Д. Сочинения в 2-х т. – Т. 2 / Д. Юм. – М.: Мысль, 1965. – 248 с.

⁷ Бондарко А.В. К вопросу о перцептивности [Текст] / А.В. Бондарко // Сокровенные смыслы: Слово. Текст. Культура: сб. статей в честь Н.Д. Арутюновой / Отв. ред. Ю.Д. Апресян. – М.: Языки славянской культуры, 2004. – С. 276–282.

⁸ Веселовский А.Н.Историческая поэтика М.:Высшая школа.1989.404 с.

⁹ Скляревская Г.Н.Метафора в системе языка .СПб.:Наука ,1993.С.52-53.(151с). Ульманн С.Семантические универсалии//Новое в лингвистике .Вып.V(Языковые универсалии).М.:Прогресс,1970.С.279.(С,250-290.)

¹⁰ . Ульманн С.Семантические универсалии//Новое в лингвистике .Вып.V(Языковые универсалии).М.:Прогресс,1970.С.279.(С,250-290.)

metaphorization of sensory perceptual qualities is at a high level, they adapt quickly with horses of different appearance and cause many changes in the meanings of horses to occur.¹¹

It is known that we can see that the emergence of various theories related to tactile qualities is the result of the mutual integration of psychology and Linguistics. Nevertheless, the analysis of tactile qualities from the point of view of psychology and linguistics is one of the important signs that indicate the perception inherent in human senses. Of course, it is also natural that the analysis of tactile qualities on the basis of language materials is somewhat complex. Because, the appeal to a number of our sensory organs to illuminate tactile qualities also requires originality. A.R.Luria also sees touch-related sensations in a person as a form consisting of simple unifying, as well as complex Elms in its composition of perception.¹² It is he who allows the first feeling: cold and heat, a feeling of pain; the second is actually tactile sensations (touch and pressure) and kinesthetic sensitivity that allow you to determine the position of your limbs in being.¹³

From observations it became known that tactile qualities also do not always have "tactile" properties, but are used synesthetically to describe areas of non-sensory perception. In metaphorical synesthesia, any perception in its first sense gives a characteristic with one or more metaphorical portable meanings to describe modality denoting modus. (Some of them are recorded in annotated dictionaries).¹⁴ The linguistic concept of human non-linguistic (extralinguistic) perception carries out expression (through the prism of language).¹⁵ The interest in Cognitive Research means that the disclosure and classification of their mechanisms consists in showing their role in the existence of non-linguistic identities using various linguistic means. G.In Paul's interpretation: "metaphor is such a phenomenon that it applies in a figurative sense, which inevitably occurs in human nature, not only in the body, but even in everyday human communication, an epithet that expresses the color –perfection of various phrases", metaphor - "a means that fills the kemptic space of expression at this point and saves"¹⁶ The term metaphor suggests that science was originally brought into existence by the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotel. He uses the term metaphor in his work "Poetics". "Metaphor is a vulgar name, being considered a displacement. The phenomenon of transition from genus to species, or from species to genus, in another situation from species to species, is analogy."¹⁷ In other words, metaphor as a method of analogy is manifested in the revision of the basic meaning of a word.

It should be noted that although the phenomenon of metaphor has been studied from the philological science of the world for more than two thousand years, it has not been largely excluded from the field of badiyat, from the field of Stylistics, rhetoric, even more precisely,

¹¹ Шрамм А.Н. Очерки по семантике качественных прилагательных (на материале современного русского языка). Л.: Изд-во Ленингр. ун-та, 1979. С.35. (132 с.)

¹² Лурия А.Р. Лекции по общей психологии. СПб. Питер, 2003. С.129. (320 с.)

¹³ Лурия А.Р. Лекции по общей психологии. СПб. Питер, 2003. С.130. (320 с.)

¹⁴ Smirnova T. Synesthetic Metaphors: Aspects of Intralingual and Interlingual Translation// Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences. 2016. Vol. 231. Pp. 40 – 45. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.09.069>. (In Eng.).

¹⁵ Апресян Ю.Д. Избранные труды. Лексическая семантика [Текст] / Ю.Д. Апресян. 2-е изд., испр. и доп. – М.: Школа «Языки русской культуры», РАН, 1995. – Т. 1. – 472 с. Арутюнова Н.Д. Язык и мир человека. М.: «Языки русской культуры» – М., 1999. – 896 с.

¹⁶ Бюлер К. Теория языка [Текст] / К. Бюлер. – М.: Прогресс, 1993. С.317. (– 501 с.)

¹⁷ Аристотель. Сочинения: в 4 т. – Т.1. [Текст] / Аристотель. – М.: Мысль, 1976. С.45. (– 449 с.)

until the beginning of the last century, the interpretation of metaphor as a phenomenon alien to science,¹⁸

When the materials of the Uzbek language are studied, the meaning properties of tactile qualities associated with emotion are fully covered. In other words, the main vectors tactile - visual synesthesia (synesthetic transfer of the meaning of tactile qualities through visual sensation to the field of visual perception) are analyzed tactile -taste, tactile -sound, tactile olfactor (smell -cognition).¹⁹ We came to the conclusion that within the framework of the analysis of the synesthetic application of tactile qualities in Uzbek, the phenomenon of the transition of this phenomenon from the appearance of tactile perception to visual perception occurs in close association with one. Tactile -taste qualities in our language are formed quantitatively from different characters, and semantically tactile sensations bring different portable meanings to the surface within the framework of taste. From observations it is known that tactile qualities with a synesthetic displacement, in which the taste associated with Touch is expressed, are considered to have a wide expression of meaning in Uzbek. As you know, in the process of studying the collected materials, empiric data showed that five models of taste sensations: touch -taste sensation (soft meat, soft cheese); taste -olfactory sensation (aroma, pleasant smell, unpleasant smell); taste -auditory sensation (pleasant Bell, sweet voice); taste-visual sensation (spicy print, tandir meat); taste-sensory perception (pleasant music, intoxicating music).

In conclusion, the arrival of tactile qualities in a portable sense is a dynamic process, in which the problem of filling in lexical tools is seen in the study and analysis of similar models in Uzbek and other languages. It can be said that the specificity of such a feature in adjectives is due to the ontological nature of tactile sensations and means some sign. It will be necessary to analyze tactile qualities based on the national characteristics of the Uzbek language and study in the process of synesthetic migration from one sensory -sensory to another sensory-sensory.

¹⁸ Маҳмудов Н. Тил тилсими тадқиқи.-Т., Mumtoz zo's. 2017. 118-6. (166-6.)

¹⁹ Челай О.В. Концептуализация вкусовых ощущений в естественном языке. Дисс. уч. степ. канд. филолог. наук. М. 2017. С.

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